

THE RELATION BETWEEN SSC(F, K) AND Q(M) CONDITIONS

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Let Γ –be some family of curves in $\mathbb{C}$. A nonnegative Borel function ρ is called the admissibility metric of the family Γ if

$$\int_{\gamma} \rho(z)|dz| \geq 1,$$

for every $\gamma \in \Gamma$. The modulus of the family Γ is defined by the formula

$$M(\Gamma) = \frac{1}{2i} \iint_{\mathbb{C}} |\rho(z)|^2 dz \wedge d\bar{z}$$

where inf is taken over the class of all possible metrics ρ . For a pair of continua $E_1, E_2 \subset D$, the symbol $M(E_1, E_2, D)$ denotes the modulus of the family of all curves in D connecting E_1 and E_2 . The direction of the square Q will be called an angle ϕ , $0 \leq \phi \leq \frac{\pi}{2}$ such that when turning to an angle ϕ , the square Q is transformed into a square whose sides are parallel to the coordinate axes.

Definition 1 [3]. We say that a homeomorphism $f : D \rightarrow f(D)$ satisfies in the direction ϕ the strong square condition $SSC(f, K)$ with constant K if the inequality

$$M(f(E), f(F), f(D)) \leq K$$

holds for any square $Q, \bar{Q} \subset D$ with direction ϕ . Here E and F are parallel to the side of the square Q .

An ordered quadruple of pairwise distinct points in $z_k \in C, k = 1,2,3,4$, is called a tetrad. The value

$$\langle z_1 : z_2 : z_3 : z_4 \rangle = \frac{S(z_1, z_2) \cdot S(z_3, z_4)}{S(z_1, z_3) \cdot S(z_2, z_4)}$$

is called the absolute double ratio of the quadruple of points or, more briefly, the characteristic of the tetrad here $S(z, w)$ means the spherical height between the points z and w .

On the plane, consider the families $\{Q\}$ of all squares whose sides are parallel to the coordinate axes.

Let T be a family of all notebooks (fours of points) $\{z_1, z_2, z_3, z_4\}$ such that the pair of points $\{z_1, z_2\}, \{z_3, z_4\}$ lie on opposite sides of some square $Q \in \{Q\}$.

Definition 2 [2]. A homeomorphism $f : \mathbb{C} \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$ satisfies the condition $Q(M)$ with a constant depending on M if for any tetrad $\{z_1, z_2, z_3, z_4\} \in T$ the inequality

$$\begin{aligned} & |f(z_1) - f(z_2)| \cdot |f(z_3) - f(z_4)| \\ & \leq Q(M) \cdot |f(z_1) - f(z_3)| \cdot |f(z_2) - f(z_4)|. \end{aligned}$$

The following takes place

Theorem 1. Let $f : \mathbb{C} \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$ be a smooth mapping that satisfies the condition $SSC(f, K)$ with constant depend on K and $grad f(z_0) \neq 0$ at the point $z_0 \in \mathbb{C}$, then there exists a neighborhood $U(z_0, r)$ of the point z_0 it satisfies the condition $Q(M)$ with a constant depending on M linearly depending only on K in $U(z_0, r)$.

Theorem 2. Let $f : \mathbb{C} \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$ be a smooth mapping that satisfies the condition $SSC(f, K)$ with a constant depending on K and there is a constant $c, C \in (0, +\infty)$ such that $c \leq |grad f(z)| \leq C$ for all $z \in \mathbb{C}$, then it satisfies the condition $Q(M)$ with a constant depending on M linearly depending only on K .

References

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